

TI: Engineering the microstructure of biopolymer hydrogel particle dispersions to deliver functionality in foods

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Graphical Abstract:

Mastering food biopolymer particle dispersions requires understanding across multiple length scales.

**Suspension
Level**

**Microstructure
Level**

**Biopolymer
Level**

1.0 Abstract:

Biopolymer hydrogel particles provide a wide range of advantages to food applications due to their highly hydrophilic nature, the ability to tailor micro- / macro- structure and their complex rheology as dispersions. In food, dispersions of crosslinked hydrogel particles are increasingly used to create unique appearances or textures, novel aroma experiences and/or for controlled release applications. Mastering food biopolymer particle dispersions requires understanding of biopolymer physicochemistry, controlled microstructure creation, understanding the particle interactions that govern flow behaviour and the characterisation techniques that give insight into the structure-function relationships across the different length scales. In the present review, recent progress in crosslinked food biopolymer hydrogels across these domains is presented with a particular focus on fluid gel dispersions and controlled release. We highlight how emerging technologies/techniques might enable new microstructural understanding or designer biopolymer sequences. Finally, we highlight how these developments help to fully unlock biopolymer hydrogel dispersions for food applications.

2.0 Introduction

Biopolymer hydrogels pose many interests for colloid scientists ranging from: i) the fundamentals of biopolymer-biopolymer interactions involved in the formation in single and multi- biopolymer hydrogels, ii) the dynamics of hydrogel structuring during gelation, particularly in phase separating systems, iii) the forming of biopolymer hydrogels into discrete micro/macrosopic structures, iv) the interactions between biopolymer microgel particles in dispersions and with biological surfaces and v) the transport of (small) molecules within biopolymer hydrogels. Biopolymer hydrogels can exist as bulk gels (i.e., jelly gummies, gelatine tablets etc) or as particles (i.e., core shell beads, faux caviar, or fluid gel dispersions). The focus of the present article is on food hydrogel particles because of the diverse colloidal science challenges that individual particles and their dispersions bring.

There have been a number of excellent reviews on the topic of hydrogels in the past ten years.[1, 2] Our aim in the present article is to cover the recent and topical advances in the field of “food hydrogel particles” and aim to highlight a number of future perspectives. By “hydrogel particles” we are speaking of crosslinked biopolymer structures in the range of tens of microns to mm in diameter which can exist as (dilute or concentrated) dispersions in water. Hydrogel particles are interesting on three board length scales: the polymer level (cross link chemistry), the microstructure level (porosity, surface roughness) and at the dispersion level (particle-particle interactions). At the polymer level interest is often focused on the polymer cross-link chemistry and similar and dis-similar polymer-polymer interactions. Creating and controlling the microstructure of hydrogel particles continues to see high activity with a focus on microfluidic manufacturing approaches. Dispersions of hydrogel particles hold key interest in terms of mechanisms by which fluid gels pack and flow. Finally, but of most importance is the challenge of how to characterise hydrogel particles across these three length scales. The following introduces the key topics and recent progress in these four domains as they relate to food biopolymers using two disparate examples of controlled release (single hydrogel particles) and fluid gels (hydrogel particle dispersions) to highlight the colloids/materials science of interest.

3.0 How hydrogel particles are made

3.1 Hydrogel Materials – Food Biopolymers

The study of the ability of different biopolymers to form crosslinked hydrogel structures of tailorable microstructure has existed for over 10 decades, with intense research only starting in the late 1980s. There are several crosslink types for the creation of food hydrogels including i) hydrogen bonding, ii) ionic cross-linking and iii) covalent cross-linking.

Polymer-polymer hydrogen bonding plays a key role in the gelation mechanisms of many cross-linked biopolymer gels. Agar and gelatine are examples where the gelation mechanisms rely solely on hydrogen bonding. Like most red seaweed derived (galactopyranose rich) polysaccharides gelation of agar starts by the disordered polymer coil forming an ordered helix, with subsequent helix-helix aggregation to form thick bundles creating the network structure. The nature of the polymer-polymer and polymer-water hydrogen bonding is so strong that the gels withstand elevated temperatures, only melting at ~85 °C.[3] Gelatine is similar to agar in that its gelation occurs via a random coil→helix transition. The unique aspect of gelatine is the formation of a triple helix (tropocollagen rod) crosslinks separated by loosely folded non-helical domains. The triple helix is formed when three proline II peptide segments (regions high in proline, hydroxyproline and glycine) coil around one another to form a right handed triple helix (**Figure 1Ai**).[4] The triple helix structure is naturally stabilised by a number of interchain hydrogen bonds (**Figure 1Aii**) which leads to a relatively low melting point (~32°C). A number of groups have worked to further stabilise the gelatine triplex helix via chemical cross-linking using transglutaminase, polyphenol cross-linking or genipin.[4] An interesting observation is that gelatine does not contain cystine, which naturally crosslinks proteins through a disulfide bond.

Ionic cross linking of hydrogels covers several polysaccharides (alginate, carrageenan, low methoxy-pectin, low acetyl gellan) where crosslinking occurs via a combination of ionic and electrostatic interactions. Alginate is a key example of pure ionic cross-linking where divalent ions (esp. calcium) bind with carboxylate of (mainly) guluronate units to form the “egg-box” structure (**Figure 1B**).[5] The gelation of low methoxy pectin follows the same mechanism where ionic interactions between calcium and the carboxylate of galacturonic acid also lead to “egg-box” cross link structure. The carrageenan family

(kappa κ , iota ι , lambda λ) of polysaccharides are a great example of hybrid cross linking, where both ionic and electrostatic interactions are involved.[3] Carrageenan's gelation process starts with a random coil→(double)helix transition followed by ionic cross-linking of these helices to form the gel structure.[3] The ion induced cross-linking of carrageenan involves a mixture of ionic and electrostatic forces and depends on the degree of galactan sulfation.[3] The cross linking of highly sulfated ι -carrageenan involves purely electrostatic cross linking (sulfate:Ca⁺). Whilst potassium cross-linking of κ -carrageenan involves a mixture of ionic (sulfate:K⁺) and electrostatic (ether:K⁺) interactions.[3]

Covalent cross linking of biopolymers to form hydrogels is typically focussed on the reaction of amino acid side chains on adjacent protein strands (**Figure 1C**). Protein hydrogels have the advantage that they can achieve much lower porosity compared to polysaccharide hydrogels which is often sought after for controlled release applications.[6] Cysteine residues naturally react with each other to form disulfide crosslinks at pH's where there is significant deprotonation (thiolate) (**Figure 1Ci**). Hydrogel particles of diverse microstructures can be readily made from proteins that are rich in cysteine (bovine serum albumin) or have a free reactive cysteine (beta-lactoglobulin).[1, 7] Lysine and glutamine amino acids can also be covalently linked using the enzyme transglutaminase (**Figure 1Cii**).[4] Hydrophobic interactions also play a role in the cross-linking of protein based hydrogels. Unfolding of proteins during heating leads to exposure of hydrophobic residues which often triggers protein-protein aggregation as is the case for α -lactalbumin.[8, 9] The amphiphilic nature of proteins is also useful when trying to entrap emulsions or hydrophobic actives inside protein based biopolymer hydrogels. Whilst any protein can be cross-linked using transglutaminase, research on hydrogels has typically focussed on cross linking of soy and gelatine.[4] Genipin is a natural aglycone that is increasingly being used to cross link proteins, collagen, and chitosan.[10] Genipin spontaneously reacts with free amines to form a genipin modified amine (Figure 1Ciii). Cross-linking then occurs either via further reaction of the genipin (e.g. chitosan) or by reaction with a second genipin modified biopolymer (e.g. gelatine).[10]

A challenge for the food industry is the limited number of new materials for the creation of hydrogels. Furthermore, the environmental impact of existing biopolymers (e.g. gelatine) is of increasing concern to consumers. Given the role that food and nutraceuticals play in our daily lives, it is essential that they are inherently safe for

consumption and have improved sustainability credentials. Food safety assessments require rigorous chemical, digestion, and toxicological characterisation. An expense that is rarely justified by the outcomes being targeted. New approaches rather than new polymers are needed to achieve more tailored performance. There are several prospects for the advancement of hydrogel design either through combinations of materials or the development of new materials. Such approaches could lie in combinations of biopolymers (i.e., cogels or interpenetrating network gels), design of protein sequences, precision fermentation, or DNA based hydrogels.

Figure 1: Schematic representations of the different crosslinking chemistries that can be used for making biopolymer hydrogel (particles). **A)** Hydrogen bonding of a gelatine triple helix,[4] **B)** calcium crosslinking of alginate to form the "egg-box" microstructural model,[5] **C)** covalent crosslinking of proteins via **i)** disulfide bonds, **ii)** transglutaminase cross linking of glutamate and lysine amino acid side chains and **iii)** Genipin crosslinking of amines on proteins and chitosan,[4] and **D)** self-assembly of tailored DNA strands via hydrogen bonding of specific base pairs.[11]

For example, gelatine is an ideal polymer for controlling the porosity of hydrogels with average mesh sizes between 170 and 10 nm readily achievable.[12] A key limitation of gelatine hydrogels is that the H-bonded triple helix melts at 32°C eliminating its gel structure.[4] In contrast carrageenan based hydrogels have tuneable melting points but are extremely porous (having a concentration dependant average mesh size ~100

nm).[13] By combining the two, Wooster *et al* created a low porosity hydrogel with tuneable melting point for use in oral immunoglobulin delivery.[14, 15] Such combinations are not immediately obvious because biopolymer mixtures tend to undergo phase separation (spontaneously demix).¹[16-20] A miscible blend of two (bio)polymers is very rare (almost considered an exception in polymer mixing) but can occur if both:[21]

$$\Delta G_m = \Delta H_m - T\Delta S_m < 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\left(\frac{\delta^2 \Delta G_m}{\delta x_i^2}\right)_{T,P} > 0 \quad (2)$$

Where: ΔG_m is the Gibbs free energy of mixing, ΔH_m is the enthalpy of mixing, ΔS_m is the entropy of mixing, T is the temperature, and x_i is the mole fraction.

Since for (bio)polymers the entropy of mixing contribution is small, this means that the enthalpic contribution plays an important role.[21] The enthalpy of mixing can be lowered if there is favourable interactions between the two (bio)polymers (i.e. via hydrogen bonding). For criteria 2 to be met ΔG_m vs. x_i needs to be concave up, which means that the system cannot lower its energy by separating into two phases. However, too strong a polymer-polymer interaction can lead to complex coacervation and precipitation of the polymers ... a fine balancing act! An increasing number of groups are identifying combinations of biopolymers whose compatibilities favour the formation of semi-interpenetrating networks (s-IPN) rather than phase separated complex coacervates.[14, 15, 22]

The field of biomedicine has seen a rapid revolution in the creation of 'design at will' materials using DNA self-assembly at its base.[11] The specificity of base pairing rules when combined with at will sequence design has led to the creation of a variety of designer structures such as DNA origami, DNA spring and most relevant for this article DNA hydrogels.[11] DNA hydrogels are 3D self-assembled structures made up of branched DNA motifs (X, Y, T motifs) that facilitate the formation of a cross linked structure.[23] A range of programmable functionalities have been developed by inserting thermal, pH, adenosine triphosphate (ATP) or insulin responsive motifs and ligating with T4 DNA ligase to form using cross-linked DNA hydrogels. To date the smallest average mesh sizes achievable are in the range of 25 nm,[24] which are still a bit larger than the

¹ At the biopolymer concentrations needed to form a continuous hydrogel (typically > 1 wt.%).

smallest mesh sizes achievable with food biopolymer hydrogels (5 nm).[12] DNA self-assembly offers vast opportunities for hydrogel design, but there are a lot of very important open questions with respect to their use in food.

3.2 Hydrogel Particle Fabrication Processes

The creation of a cross-linked hydrogel typically involves passing the sol-gel transition under controlled conditions to create particles of desired shape and microstructural complexity. Triggering the sol-gel transition typically occurs via cooling or via mixing with a cross linker solution (e.g., Calcium, Ca^{2+}). Several processes have been used to control particle morphology including simple shear of bulk liquids (**Figure 2A**), emulsion templating (**Figure 2B**), dripping/extrusion (**Figure 2C**) or more recently microfluidic emulsion templating (**Figure 2D**). The processes of these manufacturing methods are described in the following sections, taking examples of different cross-linked hydrogels

3.2.1 Cooling under shear – Fluid gels

Fluid gels are jammed suspensions of biopolymer particles obtained by applying shear during the sol-gel transition of a hydrocolloid.[25] Fluid gels can be seen as a sub-class of microgels. Often microgels are defined as colloidal particles and sometimes restricted to gels based on covalent bonds in current literature. In this article we use the word microgel and fluid gels interchangeably and thus it also includes microgels based on physical bonds, e.g. ionic in nature, as well as microgel particles with sizes up to several hundred micrometers. Typically, the sol-gel transition is triggered by a change in temperature or by mixing with a gelling agent (e.g., multivalent ions). Fluid gels have been extensively studied over the past 25 years and have been created using a wide variety of hydrocolloids, among them low acyl gellan gum, agar, agarose, κ -carrageenan, alginate. Fluid gels can also be formed using specific proteins.[7] The shear rate should be large enough to disrupt the forming gel into gel particles which introduces a characteristic length scale typically in the order of 10 to 100 μm . The length scale is determined by a balance between the hydrodynamic force induced by the shear and the strength of the crosslink 'bonds' (either of physical or chemical nature). The two relevant time scales are the kinetics of the sol-gel transition and the hydrodynamic time scale defined by the shear on the order of a fluid gel particle diameter.

The size and shape of the resulting fluid gel particles depends on the specific hydrocolloid, its concentration, the shear rate, the cooling rate (in general the rate at which the thermodynamic condition changes from the solution phase to the gel phase),

and the gelling mechanism (e.g., parameters like the ionic strength or the Ca^{2+} concentration). Although there are some studies and examples on how shape and size depend on these conditions,[26-29] a more systematic understanding on how shear influences the sol-gel transition, and the microstructure of the final fluid gel particles is still lacking.

Figure 2: Schematic representations of the different processes used for the manufacture of crosslinked food biopolymer hydrogel particles. **A)** shear processes used in emulsion templating of fluid gel manufacture,[1] **B)** simple dripping process where alginate (or other) solution is dripped into a calcium chloride solution to induce ionic crosslinking,[2] **C)** jet cutter process where a biopolymer solution jet is cut into “rods” by the disc’s cutting wires.[30] The droplets “relax” into spherical shapes and are subsequently gelled either via cooling or in a calcium bath, and **D)** Step or EDGE (Edge-based droplet generation) microfluidic (emulsion) templating process where highly controlled biopolymer drops/spheres are created due to Rayleigh instability caused by their deformation during transit from the wedge shaped distribution nozzle, over the step and into the channel.[31]

3.2.2 Emulsion templating & Microfluidics - Step/EDGE emulsification

Emulsion templating is a widely investigated method used to produce hydrogel beads. The central concept is the dispersion of a biopolymer containing water phase in a suitable

oil phase to create a water in oil emulsion (**Figure 2A**). Originally emulsion templating processes focussed on simple shear homogenisation (magnetic stirrer) or phase inversion processes followed by cooling.[1] Key advantages of emulsion templating are the high encapsulation efficiency of small molecule actives, fast mixing between ions and biopolymers and the creation of spherical beads due to surface tension effects. Emulsion templating approaches have also enabled the creation of intricate hydrogel internal structures because physical confinement impacts phase separation of gelatine/maltodextrin mixtures.[32] By controlling the droplet size, cooling kinetics and polymer concentrations, gelatine continuous, biphasic, core-shell and half-moon microstructures have been created.[33] A significant limitation of shear based emulsion templating is that the high polydispersity of the resulting hydrogels leads to very broad release profiles in encapsulation applications.

The rise of microfluidic technology has driven an increased focus on microfluidic based emulsion templating of dispersed biopolymer hydrogels.[34-36] Microfluidic fabrication offers the key advantages of precise size control, ultra-low polydispersity and (in some devices) controlled reaction times for tailored chemical cross-linking.[36] Microfluidic fabrication processes can be classed into two domains; i) shear-based systems (Y- or T-junctions and flow focussing devices) or ii) interfacial tension-driven spontaneous emulsification devices (such as the Step, EDGE (Edge-based droplet generation) devices).[35] There has been extensive use of microfluidics in the fabrication of cross-linked hydrogels esp. based on alginate. Shear based devices are often explored for the creation of multi-laminar structures.[34] Flow focusing devices have been shown to be particularly suited to the creation of core-shell hydrogel structures.[34] Such core shell structures further enhance the controlled release benefits of microfluidic fabricated hydrogels.[34]

Whilst microfluidic based emulsion templating approaches gained a lot of attention during the early 2000s, their scalability was a key factor limiting their true potential. However, simultaneous developments in the parallelisation of step (spontaneous) emulsification appear to have unlocked the scalability problem of microfluidic based emulsion templating of hydrogels.[31, 35, 37] Droplets are formed in spontaneous microfluidic devices due to the sudden drop in Laplace pressure that occurs when the dispersed stream passes from a shallow channel into the deep reservoir (**Figure 2D**).[38] Hydrogel beads can then be formed either via temperature drop, reaction with calcium or potassium.[39] Two teams demonstrated different ways of parallelising the step

approach and can now achieve droplet production rates of $0.4 - 25 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$ (EDGE) to $>100 \text{ L h}^{-1}$ (STEP).[35, 40] The Step technology is now in its commercial infancy with the Microcaps start-up which promises manufacturing of 1kg of capsules per day at bench scale. Microcaps are already gaining success in food (faux caviar), cosmetic and pharma domains based on its alginate hydrogel technology.[41]

3.2.3 Dripping/Extrusion – Calcium Alginate spheres

The creation of alginate hydrogels involves crosslinking by calcium, as such the most common method of hydrogel manufacture is dripping an alginate solution into a calcium bath (**Figure 2B**). The extrusion of an alginate solution through an orifice creates highly uniform liquid drops. The diameter of such drops is a balance between gravitational and surface tension forces, being a function of the internal diameter and wettability of the nozzle. Upon arrival at the surface of the calcium bath the falling drop encounters several forces (inertia, bath surface tension) that lead to dramatic drop deformation. The gelation of the surface of the drop as it hits the bath surface creates highly deformed (flattened) gel bead structures often called “pancakes”. Highly spherical alginate beads can be achieved by lowering the bath surface tension via a combination of gentle stirring and low amounts of surfactant. Intricate core shell structures can be created using coextrusion.

3.2.4 Jet cutter

While standard dripping only allows production of mm-sized hydrogel beads, sizes as low as a couple of hundreds of μm can be obtained with a jet cutter (**Figure 2C**).[42-44] The jet cutter consists of a rotating disc of 24 to a couple of hundred of fine ($50\text{-}400 \mu\text{m}$) wires that cut a jet of biopolymer solution into cylindrical pieces (**Figure 2C**).[30, 42, 44, 45] The surface tension of the system causes the cylinders to rapidly form highly regular spheres. The size of the resulting hydrogel droplets is dictated by the cut tube, which is affected by the fluid jet velocity, jet diameter and cutting frequency (cutting disc rpm and number of wires). Key advantages of the jet cutter system are that it can handle high biopolymer solution viscosities (up to ca. $1 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$),[43, 46] has a high bead production rate ($>100,000$ beads/s at industrial scale),[47] can be parallelised (up to 4 units per machine)[30, 47] and can potentially be used to create intricate core-shell hydrogel structures.[30]

The exploitation of jet cutter technology for the creation of crosslinked hydrogel particles is in its infancy. So far, jet cutter technology has mostly been used to produce

alginate,[30, 43-45, 47] pectin[30, 43, 44] and chitosan[30, 42, 44, 47] beads which undergo ionic cross-linking. Most research has so far focussed on ionic cross-linking where gelation occurs in a recipient bath containing an ionic cross-linker.[30, 42-45, 47] One may think to extend its usage to produce hydrogel beads with biopolymers undergoing thermal gelation.[15] Thermal gelation would reduce encapsulant losses by reducing encapsulate leakage during gelation in the cross-linker bath. Despite its promise, there is still a lack of general understanding on how both biopolymer solution properties and process parameters influence hydrogel biopolymer bead production,[43, 46] which is why the growth of this technique has been hindered so far.

4.0 Controlled Release – discrete hydrogel particles

The formation of a hydrogel involves the cross linking of multiple polymer chains which results in a molecular scale porous mesh-like microstructure. The creation of such porous structures provides restrictions to the mass transport of molecules.[48] The controlled transport(release) of molecules through hydrogels has been a central topic in pharmaceuticals for obvious reasons. The main physics of controlled release involves the transport of molecules through the tortuous polymer mesh via restricted diffusion. Key works by Lustig, Peppas and Higuchi outline the relationship between hydrogel mesh size and the kinetics of release (equations 3-5).[48-50] These consist of several scenarios from the simple, where release is controlled by restricted diffusion through the tortuous mesh (Equations 4 and 5), to the complex where the hydrogel microstructure is swelling or eroding (either via surface or bulk) during the release process. Additional complexity arises when there is temporary adsorption of the diffusing molecules to the surface of the hydrogel (K_p in equation 4 and 6).

$$C_t = C_\infty \frac{S}{V} \sqrt{\left(\frac{D't}{\pi}\right)} \quad (3)$$

$$D' = DK_p K_r \frac{\epsilon}{\tau} \quad (4)$$

$$K_r = (1 - \lambda)^2, \lambda = \frac{D_H}{\xi}, \quad (5)$$

$$K_p = \frac{\text{Conc. on polymer}}{\text{Conc. in pore}} \quad (6)$$

Where: C_t and C_∞ are the concentration of drug released at times t and ∞ , S and V are the surface area and volume of the hydrogel particle, D and D' are the solution and effective diffusion coefficients of the drug, K_p and K_r are the partition and restriction coefficients, D_H is drugs hydrodynamic diameter (nm), and ξ is the average mesh size (nm).

The exploitation of the ability of biopolymer hydrogels to control the release of molecules has only recently been a key topic in food.[6, 12, 51-56] A key focus has been the creation of hydrogels to control the release of macromolecules during digestion. These studies have focussed on; i) hydrogel encapsulation of enzymes to protect their activity until they arrive in the intestine or ii) the use of hydrogels to slow or delay macronutrient digestion.[51]

A clever approach has been the co-encapsulation of buffer and pancreatic lipase within calcium alginate hydrogels to ensure lipase activity upon transit through the stomach.[52] People suffering from conditions such as pancreatic insufficiency syndrome or cystic fibrosis lose intestinal enzyme activity. The co-encapsulation of lipase with $Mg(OH)_2$ in an alginate hydrogel ensures it stays in a neutral pH microclimate as it transits the acidic stomach. Upon arrival in the small intestine, lipolysis activity is maintained (*in vitro*) by swelling induced diffusion release of lipase into the lumen.[52]

One of the seminal works on the use of food grade hydrogels to create tailorable release was the work of Klak et al.[51] Klak et al. exploited the natural ability of gelatine to create hydrogels of different average mesh size as a function of biopolymer concentration. With increasing biopolymer concentration the number of crosslink nodes increases leading to smaller average mesh sizes.[12] The low repulsion between gelatine chains means that highly tortuous hydrogels with concentrations up to 30% ($\xi < 5$ nm) can readily be created.[12] Klak *et al* demonstrated that gelatine hydrogels were able to dramatically slow the release of macromolecules (150 & 2000 kDa FITC-dextran). However, Klak *et al* also demonstrated that the large mesh sizes of such hydrogels (15 nm) were not able to slow the release of neutral small molecules.[53] Because of the large ratio between molecule hydrodynamic diameter (0.48-0.68 nm) and gelatine hydrogel average mesh size (15-16 nm) there was only moderate restriction of diffusion.[53] However, when alginate was introduced (as an IPN with the gelatine hydrogel) the release of positively charged small molecules was slowed due to transient binding to the hydrogel.[53] The work of Klak *et al* highlights the important impact that hybrid or IPN hydrogels can have in tailoring the properties for the final application. In this case, binding of the active ingredient to the hydrogel was more important for controlling release than the restriction of diffusion arising from the hydrogel mesh size.

Several groups have been interested in using hydrogels to control lipolysis by limiting the access of lipase to the interface of encapsulated emulsions.[12, 54, 55] Using a

variety of biopolymers (alginate, whey protein, gelatine) the different teams established a strong relationship between hydrogel mesh size and lipolysis kinetics. For example, Corstens *et al.* found a direct relationship between Ca²⁺ alginate gel average mesh size and lipase effective diffusion coefficient, which translated into a reduce speed of lipolysis decreasing with decreasing hydrogel mesh size (**Figure 3A**).[54] The relative size of lipase ~5.2 nm means that relatively porous alginate hydrogels were able to slow lipolysis. Similarly Sarkar *et al* demonstrated that the speed of lipolysis scaled inversely with the average mesh size of gelatine hydrogels, achieving a 30x reduction in lipolysis rate.[12] Sarkar *et al* highlighted the complexity of using digestible hydrogels in that the system underwent surface/bulk erosion changing the speed of restricted diffusion during the time course of the release.[12] Corstens *et al* also successfully demonstrated that use of hydrogels to limit lipid digestion led to a small reduction in energy intake (~6.2%) during the subsequent meal.[55] However, a consistent theme across this research was that mono-structure biopolymer hydrogels did not alter the initiation of lipolysis, because the fat droplets were homogeneously distributed throughout the beads.

A delay in lipolysis initiation was recently introduced using a core-shell hydrogel structure.[6, 56] The inner hydrogel consisted of gelatine gelled emulsion beads which were fabricated using millifluidic device. The outer hydrogel consisted of a phase separated blg-xanthan thermally crosslinked protein gel fabricated by moulding. The resulting structure (**Figure 3C**) created an outer hydrogel layer whose dense porosity meant that degradation occurred primarily through surface erosion.[56] Tailoring of the porosity and/or thickness of the outer biopolymer hydrogel enabled easy control of the delay in lipolysis initiation. Release of the contents within the core-shell hydrogel was "instantaneous" because of melting of the gelatine based inner hydrogel (**Figure 3D**). Such core-shell hydrogels could open a wide range of targeted delivery of different bioactives, if their bespoke fabrication processes were not so complex.

Figure 3: **A)** Confocal 3D micrograph of emulsion containing Ca^{2+} :Alginate hydrogels whose different mesh sizes effectively regulate the speed of fat digestion by reducing lipases' effective diffusion coefficient **B).** **C)** Core-shell mixed biopolymer hydrogel particle concept whose surface erosion and molten core combine to create a **D)** programable delayed burst release whose release in the lower small intestine is a function of outer biopolymer average mesh size. Images A and B reproduced with permission from Corstens et al.[54]

5.0 Fluid gels

5.1 Introduction to of Fluid gel dispersions.

As mentioned earlier fluid gels are jammed suspensions of biopolymer particles obtained by applying shear during the sol-gel transition of a hydrocolloid.[25] Fluid gels are interesting because their unique rheological properties can be used to create texture without impacting flavor.[57] In the field of pharmaceuticals fluid gels are also used and discussed as delivery systems for bioactives.[58] In this paper we do not discuss this aspect as we see only limited options to use them as delivery systems in food applications. The size and shape of fluid gel particles depends on the type of

hydrocolloid, parameters affecting the sol-gel transition like for example the Ca^{2+} concentration as well as a number of process parameters like the hydrocolloid concentration, the shear rate, the cooling rate and the viscosity of the solution.

Figure 4: Optical micrographs of fluid gels prepared from A) low acetyl gellan gelled by Calcium and B) agar gelled via cooling. Reproduced with permission from D’Oria et al.[26]

The typical size is defined by the length where the shear forces become large enough to disrupt the gel crosslinks and, by that, limit further growth of the fluid gel particles. Typical sizes range from around 10 μm to several 100 μm . The first example of low acyl gellan gum fluid gels (LA gellan gum 0.1%, shear rate 500 1/s, cooling rate -0.5 Kelvin per second K/s) shows large highly non-spherical particles with sizes around 500 μm and arms with a length of 100 to 500 μm . [26] The second example of agar fluid gel (agar 0.4%, shear rate 500 1/s, colling rate -0.5 K/s) shows smaller, more spherical star-like microgel particles with a size of around 50 μm and arms with a length of 20 μm . [26]. Much smaller fluid gel particles well below 10 μm have also been reported in the literature. [28] One still should note that most size measurements are based on light microscopy of fluid gels at very high dilution in order to be able to differentiate individual fluid gel particles (Figure 4). In applications fluid gels are at a much higher, space filling density and the exact size in this state can only be estimated indirectly so far.

In the past 25 years a large number of studies have investigated the creation and the properties of fluid gels made from different hydrocolloids as well as proteins: low acyl gellan gums [25, 26, 59-61], κ -Carrageenan, [29, 62] Alginate, [57] Agar, [26, 63], Xanthan gum, [64] Gelatin, [65] or whey protein. [7] These studies illustrate that fluid gels can be created from biopolymers which exhibit a wide range of gelling mechanisms. Physical gelling mechanisms include biopolymers that show a random coil \rightarrow helix transition

followed by a helix-helix aggregation step.[63, 65]. The helix-helix aggregation step can be electrostatic in nature, e.g., low acyl gellan gum or driven by van-der-Waals forces as in the case of agar. Examples of fluid gels based on chemical crosslinking are whey proteins (di-sulfate bonds).[57]

5.2 Rheology of Fluid Gel Dispersions.

Fluid gels exhibit some rather interesting rheology due to the physical structuring and discrete nature of the microgel particles. The addition of the mesostructured particle network provokes transient network formation at a super-colloidal scale such that there is no thermal relaxation mechanism. Hence fluid gels have microscale properties on the scale of a single, continuous gel particle, and non-ergodic, mesoscale properties on the scale of the transient particle network. Consequently, fluid gels at rest exhibit gel like properties like elasticity with storage modulus, $G' >$ relaxation modulus, G'' in the linear viscoelastic regime and are able to suspend particles, e.g., showing a significant yield stress. On the other hand, fluid gels behave like a liquid and already flow under their own weight. In this regime it shows strong shear thinning behavior. In this 'fluid gel' concentration regime we hypothesize that the fluid gel particles are filling the entire fluid volume (the fluid gel particle network is space filling or at least percolating). This fluid gel concentration regime has not yet been fully determined, but upon dilution at some point the typical fluid gel properties, e.g., the ability to suspend particles, disappear. Due to the soft nature of the gel particles and their ability to swell it is not straight forward to define a volume fraction ϕ . Still, using an effective volume fraction ϕ_{eff} , the apparent viscosity at a given shear rate shows the typical behavior of a dense suspension of soft particles following the Krieger-Dougherty relation.[66]

On longer time scales fluid gels show ageing phenomena analogous to soft glasses.[67] For example G' increases over time proportional to $\log(t)$. This change in time of a fundamental material property destroys the time translational invariance and is rooted in the inability of the system to explore the phase space or in other words is not in thermal equilibrium. This behavior has been coined 'soft glass rheology' in the seminal paper of Fielding et al.[67] The behavior has been well studied for model systems forming soft glasses.[68-70] Recently this behavior has also been demonstrated for fluid gels.[26] The system is studied using an ageing – rejuvenation cycle that enables the observation of a large number of individual glass configurations.[68] The associated slowing down of the average relaxation times has been shown to follow a Kohlrausch-Williams-Watts stretched exponential model.[26, 71, 72]

The ageing behavior is similar for fluid gel systems with both ion mediated crosslinks as well as non-ionic mediated crosslinks and is also independent of the magnitude of gravity. The latter one has been tested by varying the density of the fluid gels by embedding silica particles into the fluid gel.[26] Microscale properties are those of a conventional hydrocolloid gel, i.e., an isotropic yield stress as would be observed for a continuum gel. These properties can be observed at sub particle scales with micro-indentation techniques such as atomic force microscopy (AFM), but cannot be directly measured with conventional shear rheometry.[40, 60] Mesoscale properties are similar to those of a soft, wet, granular material and, as such, considerable care must be taken to achieve meaningful rheological characterization. Granular materials are generally governed by frictional contacts between particles, which in the current case (and almost always) are a consequence of gravity. Since gravity is a vector, the material response to shear stresses is inherently anisotropic and depends on the direction of the imposed deformation. The net effect of this underlying physics is that apparent rheology of the 'effective bulk fluid gel' is dependent on depth of sample and direction of applied load. As a consequence, traditional shear rheometry will not be sufficient to fully elucidate and to characterize the static, or small amplitude strain properties of fluid gel materials.

The physical biopolymer network that results in the gel-structure of hydrocolloids (Gellan, etc.) that are relevant in the current context is generally due to bivalent cations bridging negatively charged sites on different chains. This is not a permanent covalent bond, so there is a certain persistence time, and these bonds are dynamically forming and breaking such that the net equilibrium is maintained. There will therefore always be a certain population of 'gelled' regions and unconnected 'sol' fragments, existing as single, or small clusters of chains. The 'sol' fraction of biopolymer effectively functions as a continuous solvent phase for the rest of the material, and, as such, can result in significant amounts of background shear viscosity. This is 'true' shear viscosity, in the sense that it is isotropic and exists in the absence of frictional gel particle contacts. It will manifest in shear rheometry as would a suspension and it can be quantified in that fashion.

Given that the bonds between chains are continuously forming, breaking, and reforming, there are always going to be a certain number of 'free' bonding sites available. Consequently, bonds can conceptually form between adjacent gel fragments if they are in close contact for long enough. It is difficult to predict how fast this process

will occur, but theory would suggest that the rate would be proportional to the number of free sites, which is in turn related to the underlying physical chemistry of the gelling system. Experience suggests that strongly gelled systems, such as alginate and gellan, are less prone to sticking together than soft systems such as pectin. Practical observations seem to align with the expectation arising from the theory. In addition, it will be important to study this aspect further for example by comparing properties of fluid gels created with hydrocolloids with physical crosslinks to fluid gels based on hydrogels with chemical crosslinks.

Density differences between gelled particles and background fluid presumably drive both the sedimentation rate, and the frictional forces between the sedimented gel particles. It is unclear from a thermodynamical perspective how such density differences arise, since chain entropy should be relatively independent of whether or not a particular chain is linked or free from its neighbors. Given the wet granular nature of fluid gels, it is relatively easy to see why they can suspend relatively dense and substantial inclusions in a quiescent state – essentially the inclusions are trapped in a non-relaxing pile of gel particles (a particle glass). It should be noted that the suspension properties only occur when the weight of the inclusion creates a stress lower than the yield stress of an individual gel particle. Any greater stresses will just ‘flow’ through the gel particle as if it doesn’t exist—in contrast to a typical granular material such as a sand pile. Pouring the fluid gel removes the frictional contacts and fluid like behavior is transiently observed until the quiescent network reforms once the motion arrests.

One of the most important properties for fluid gels for the applications in food is their dilution behavior. As previously noted, from a thermodynamic perspective, chains are relative agnostic to their bonding state, such that a free chain and a cross-linked chain have very similar amounts of entropy. If this is true, then the system entropy is substantially determined by the concentration of chains relative to solvent. Consequently, if the bulk fluid, including the free biopolymer is diluted, then the concentration decreases, and hence system entropy will increase. Chains that are tethered within a gel fragment will need to match this entropy change as much as possible, so they will stretch and suck in more solvent. As the tethered gels swell, the chains will become stretched, so the process is ultimately limited by the loss of chain entropy at some point. One must remember that biopolymers are polyelectrolytes and there are many counterions in the solvent phase, such that the real situation is massively more complex than the toy model just described. As mentioned previously, the calcium

bonding is a reversible, transient process, and as such bonds are likely to form between adjacent particles over time. This seems not to have been investigated in any detail, although our experience suggests that there are significant differences observable between fluid gels made from different hydrocolloids.

Despite the significant work that has been published on fluid gel systems there are still a number of intriguing questions that have not been answered. The first one is related to the fact that fluid gel particles (created using shear during the sol gel transition) do not behave like quiescent gels that have been fractured after gelation (applying shear after the sol-gel transition). There are several possible explanations for this: The shear during the sol-gel transition could also lead to a non-isotropic gel, e.g., the mesh-size could become a direction dependent tensor instead of a scalar. The same reason can also lead to anisotropic gel particle shapes, something that indeed can be seen in microscopy images of stained fluid gel particles.[26] Again based on microscopy images, fluid gel particles exhibit a very rough, ragged surface with visible arm like structures of colloidal nature (thickness of the order of 1 to 10 μm and length of up to several 100 μm). In analogy to rubber-based materials, like car tyres, it is well known that microscopic particle coating is often the key factor determining macroscopic material properties.

The second one concerns the question to which extent properties of fluid gels are based on the material properties of the individual fluid gel particles on one hand – see microscale properties above - and on the collective properties mediated by the interactions between the fluid gel particles on the other hand – see mesoscale properties above. So far studies on the microscopic properties of individual fluid gel particles are sparse and studies on the interaction between, for example, a pair of fluid gel particles are completely absent. For the latter one could employ the well-established technique of using optical tweezers to study the interaction potential between two individual particles as a function of inter particle distance.

A third question concerns our discussion above regarding the importance of the transient nature of the crosslinks (physical crosslinks) in some of the most well studied fluid gels (e.g., gellan gum) in contrast with fluid gels created with material forming chemical crosslinks.

6.0 Recent advances in Microstructure characterization of hydrogel particles and hydrogel particle suspensions

The creation of cross-linked hydrogel particle dispersions requires detailed understanding at the biopolymer (nanometer), particle (micron) and dispersion (mm) length scales. This requires a range of techniques that can shed light on biopolymer cross-link chemistry, hydrogel network microstructure, particle size and shape and dispersion flow behavior *etc.* A number of recent reviews provide detailed descriptions of the multitude of techniques commonly used to characterize hydrogel particle dispersions, highlighting their advantages and limitations.[73-76] In Figure 5, we present an overview of these techniques organized by the length scale of the structure feature probed at, *i.e.* polymer, microstructure and dispersion levels. The figure is inspired from Patel *et al.* [73] and its supplementary material, where most of the cited techniques are well described and are therefore not discussed further here. We instead discuss techniques that have not yet been reviewed since they are either too recent (*i.e.*, small ange x-ray scattering (SAXS) and Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) for porosity measurements) or have rarely been used to characterize biopolymer hydrogel particles (*i.e.*, Raman microscopy, Super-Resolution Fluorescence Microscopy (SRFM) and Photon Correlated Imaging (PCI); see Table S1 in Supplementary Information (SI) for more information). Figure 5 also includes a review of techniques typically used to characterize fluid gel particles/dispersions (Table S1), which is, to our knowledge, the first of this kind in the literature.

Figure 5: Overview of the characterisation techniques used to investigate hydrogel particles and their suspensions showing the type of information they provide and ranked as a function of the level they

provide information with (*i.e.*, polymer, microstructure and/or suspension). ●: microgel particles/microgel suspensions; ◆, ◇: fluid gel particles/suspensions, full symbols correspond to techniques that are typically used in the literature while empty symbols correspond to techniques that have not yet been used but that we think could provide new insights.

Abbreviations: AFM: Atomic Force Microscopy; DSC: Differential Scanning Calorimetry; EDX: Energy Dispersive -X-ray; FTIR: Fourier Transform Infrared; LS: Light Scattering; NMR: Nuclear Magnetic Resonance; PCI: Photon Correlated Imaging; SANS : Small Angle Neutron Scattering; SAXS : Small Angle X-ray Scattering; SEM: Scanning Electron Microscopy; SLS: Static Light Scattering; SRFM: Super-Resolution Fluorescence Microscopy; TEM: Transmission Electron Microscopy; USAXS: Ultra Small Angle X-ray Scattering; WAXS: Wide Angle X-ray Scattering; XRD: R-Ray Diffraction.

A key parameter in controlled release is the specific surface area of hydrogel beads because it determines the surface available for active adsorption. It is commonly determined by gas sorption or mercury (Hg) porosimetry after drying of the hydrogel beads, although this is known to modify their microstructures and hence create artifacts/biases. A very recent study has established that Small Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS)/Wide Angle Scattering (WAXS) can effectively measure hydrogel bead specific surface area in a hydrated state. This study demonstrated that drying induces a reorganization of the polymer network at the nanoscale with the creation of smaller mesh sizes. The specific surface area of hydrated beads was found to be two orders of magnitude lower than that typically found for dry beads measured with conventional techniques.[77] This technique opens avenues to investigate the evolution of the specific surface area of microgels exposed to different environments to better understand solute controlled release. SAXS can also be used to study the internal structure of the hydrogel and the structure of cross link regions of different biopolymers. Small Angle Neutron Scattering (SANS) is a complementary technique to SAXS where the interaction of the source radiation with the sample (scattering cross section) varies randomly with atomic number.[78] The different scattering cross section combined with the ability to use deuterated water/biopolymer provide a wider range of scattering contrasts to enable more robust data modelling. It is worth noting that the usage of SAXS/SANS may be limited at this stage. Whilst SAXS/WAXS measurements can be performed at lab- they are more often performed at advanced light sources (exclusively the case for SANS). Furthermore SAXS measurements involve careful calibration, long acquisition times, appropriate knowledge to model the data and often require coupling with complementary methods (SANS or SALLS) to enable robust data modelling.

NMR can also be used to measure hydrogel porosity in a hydrated state. Several approaches are available therefore, including NMR relaxometry and NMR diffusometry.[79-81] They probe molecular rotational and translational mobilities, respectively, which are strongly correlated to the environment the investigated molecules are in; thus providing information about the pores they are located in. In practice, NMR relaxometry and NMR diffusometry measure proton relaxation times and diffusion coefficients, respectively. In addition to pore size determination, these techniques have been successfully used for other purposes in the field of hydrogels. For instance, NMR relaxometry can be used to identify core-shell structures of microgel particles due to the difference in mobility of the densely crosslinked chains of the core that are significantly less mobile than those of the corona.[79] Similar measurements may thus be attempted on fluid gels to confirm the structure of fluid gel particles. Furthermore, NMR diffusometry can be used to measure microgel diffusion coefficient and aggregation behaviour.[79] It can also probe diffusivity of various solutes, which is key in the field of controlled release.[80, 82]

Raman microscopy is a technique that couples a microscope with a Raman spectrometer. It creates 2D or 3D maps of a sample based on the Raman signal that is collected in the different regions of the sample. A small region of the sample is illuminated with a laser beam and the light that is inelastically scattered – which constitutes the Raman signal – is collected.[83] The same process is repeated successively for other positions in the xy-plane to obtain a 2D map, as well as in the z-plane to obtain 3D maps. In contrast to confocal microscopy or super resolution fluorescence microscopy (SRFM), it does not require fluorescent labelling. The signal is, however, fairly weak, especially for biopolymers due to their low Raman scattering cross section, and long acquisition times may be required to compensate for this.[84] Further instrumental improvements as well as the development of surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) where metallic nanoparticles (either incorporated in the sample or present at the surface of the substrate the sample is deposited on) are used to enhance the Raman signal have allowed investigation of the microstructure of hydrogels. One of the main advantages of this technique is that it allows mapping of multiple constituents in complex hydrogel matrices. Hence, gellan/ κ -carrageenan phase separated systems could be resolved and the composition of the resulting hydrogel beads could be determined.[84] More recently, the distribution of chemical and physical crosslinker and double crosslinked polymer

hydrogels was determined.[85-87] This technique would thus be useful to understand the structure of multicomponent hydrogel networks which we see as a way to develop hydrogel beads with novel properties.

Super-Resolution Fluorescence Microscopy, or nanoscopy, is an optical microscopy technique that allows probing of hydrogel nanostructure by overcoming the diffraction limit.[88-90] It emerged in the 1990s but has only started to be used in polymer science field recently.[88] As its name suggests, SRFM only probes fluorescent samples hence either the network or the solvent must be fluorescently tagged. It is the contrast between the fluorescent and the non-fluorescent regions in the sample that enables sample imaging.[91] Tagging food-grade biopolymer hydrogels is a bit less trivial than tagging synthetic polymer hydrogels, where fluorophores may be incorporated during polymer synthesis and the choice of fluorescent crosslinkers is significantly wider. However, there are a number of fluorescent tags that can interact with biopolymer hydrogels through electrostatic, van der Waals, hydrophobic or hydrogen interactions that can be used. SRFM has enabled probing of spatial heterogeneities in κ -carrageenan hydrogels and showed how they evolve over time using 28 nm size fluorescent nanoparticles[92]. Such investigations, performed on fluid gels, may help to resolve the structure of the particles they are made of, which is commonly thought to be heterogeneous with a dense core and a much less dense, hairy-like corona.[93-96] SRFM could prove to be very useful to investigate fluid gel particles *in situ* and better understand their morphology as well as their spatial organization. One interesting path could be to mix untagged fluid gel particles with a small number of fluorescently tagged fluid gel particles to visualize individual fluid gel particles whilst they are surrounded by other fluid gel particles in a similar way as what has been achieved for synthetic microgels. The motion of individual fluid gel particles may then be tracked and some of the questions about ageing phenomena in fluid gels may be answered.[97] If two different fluorescent tags can be used, the interpenetration, deformation and compression two neighboring fluid gel particles experience could be probed. In the controlled release field, SRFM may be a key complement to fluorescence recovery after photobleaching (FRAP) techniques to understand hydrogel network evolution over time, with or without *stimulus*, which could improve our understanding of phenomena such as swelling or bioactive release mechanisms. Similar approaches have been successfully applied to synthetic microgels.[98]

Photon correlation imaging (PCI) is a space-resolved Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) technique where the speckle patterns of a scattering sample are recorded at regular times and are subsequently correlated to obtain intensity auto-correlation functions that are indicative of sample microstructure dynamics.[99] Contrary to standard DLS set-ups, a significantly wider area of the samples is probed, by projecting an image of the scattering region onto a pixelated detector, *e.g.* using a charged coupled device (CCD) or a complementary metal-oxide semiconductor CMOS camera.[99-101] This not only allows to obtain statistically reliable data for samples exhibiting slow dynamics such as hydrogels but allows investigation of spatial heterogeneities since the collected images may be divided into smaller areas that can be analyzed separately. Several PCI studies have probed changes in hydrogel microstructure during and after gelation and highlighted the presence of spatial heterogeneities in quite a few cases.[102-105] Fluid gels are thought to be heterogeneous, hence PCI could help probing these heterogeneities. Information about the microstructure of the fluid gels as well as an estimation of the size of the fluid gel particles in the samples might be obtained based on the heterogeneities of scattering behavior.

Milani *et al.*[106] have recently developed a PCI set-up that allows for the investigation of the behavior of mm-size gel beads. The laser beam goes through the equatorial plane of the bead and allows to investigate how the properties of the bead alongside a bead diameter evolve over time as a function of the radial position. The set-up is coupled with a bright light imaging system that allows for simultaneous imaging of the bead. With this set-up, drying of colloidal beads has been investigated. Gelation, ageing, and bead response to various *stimuli* including temperature, pH, humidity, *etc* might also be investigated, provided that the gel bead remains stationary during the application of the *stimulus* or can be stabilized just afterwards. Hence, phenomena that are key for designing hydrogels for controlled released or understanding fluid gels such as swelling, shrinking or fragmentation could be studied and would provide useful insights for hydrogel particle formulation.

To understand the intriguing ability of fluid gel particles to swell upon dilution, and especially the kinetics of such processes, it may be interesting to have a means to vary and control the volume fraction within a sample. Such an approach has been recently developed to investigate the behavior of glass-forming colloidal suspension.[107] It consists of adding hydrogel beads able to undergo a volume phase transition upon a

stimulus. In Ref. [107], the ca. 200 μm swollen hydrogel beads are made of thermosensitive poly(N-isopropylacrylamide) (PNiPAM). At low temperatures, they are fully swollen and the colloidal suspension they are suspended in thus has a high-volume fraction, while at high temperatures, they are shrunken, and the colloidal suspension has a low volume fraction. Looking at the fluid gel samples with one of the above imaging techniques while varying the stimulus would allow for in situ investigation of the effect of either dilution or concentration.

Last but not least, although we do not discuss it here, it is worth noting that simulation tools have been developing fast over the past years and have been helpful to understand mesoscale hydrogel behavior.[76] Going to smaller scales is proving to be difficult due to the complexity of polymer hydrogel network and the lack of understanding of both particle-particle interactions and swelling-deswelling behaviors.[76] The characterization techniques highlighted above should help bring more insights about these topics, thus providing more material for modelling, which would in turn bring more understanding about hydrogel particulate material microstructure and spatial organization.

7.0 Conclusions and Future perspectives:

Biopolymer hydrogel particle dispersions provide an exciting scientific playground for the creation of designer colloids in food. Mastering food biopolymer particle dispersions requires understanding across the biopolymer, microstructure and dispersion length scales and necessitates a range of characterization techniques. In this work we present recent progress in crosslinked food biopolymer hydrogels across these domains with a particular focus on fluid gel dispersions and controlled release. Several exciting developments with respect to new biopolymers, particle fabrication, dispersion, and characterization are highlighted. The emerging ability to tailor biopolymer molecular (designer protein sequences, mixed biopolymer co-gels) and network structure (internally phase separated and core shell) combined with highly controllable fabrication techniques (EDGE microfluidics and jet cutter) promises a step change in the creation of tailored biopolymer hydrogel particles. The discovery that careful control of shear conditions during the sol-gel transition can give rise to completely new material properties as well as in-mouth sensory experiences of liquid food products will give rise to exciting new food products but also still holds up a good number of scientifically very interesting challenges. Finally, key advances in microstructure characterization techniques such as Raman microscopy, super resolution fluorescence spectroscopy and the emerging Photon Correlated Imaging (space resolved DLS) are starting to unlock multi-scale structure-function relationships (particularly in mixed systems). These advances are a few key tools in the journey to the creation of 'design at will' biopolymer particle dispersions with tunable functionality.

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Shows the potential of space resolved dynamic light scattering to probe the microstructure of polymer hydrogel dispersions.

Supplementary Information to

Engineering the microstructure of biopolymer hydrogel particle dispersions to deliver functionality in foods

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This document contains two tables which provide details about the newly characterisation techniques proposed for hydrogel particles/suspensions and fluid gel characterisation and characterisation techniques that have been used in the fluid gel field so far. They are both built in a similar way as the table presented in Ref. [1] and its supplementary information.

Table S1: Details about newly proposed characterisation techniques proposed for hydrogel particles/suspensions and fluid gel characterisation

Technique Probe [Ref]	Sample preparation	Information obtained over length scale	Resolution/detection limit, field of view, magnification	Advantages	Disadvantages, damage to sample	Information specific to microgels/mesogels <i>Suggested use for the study of fluid gels</i>
Raman microscopy (Direct and indirect)	None, except for Surface- Enhanced- Raman- Scattering	Hydrogel spatial composition (qualitative and quantitative), identification of	Lateral resolution: 1- 2 μm z-resolution: up to a couple of μm ; it	Direct observation of the samples without staining nor dyeing like in	Raman signal is weak by nature. This is especially true for biopolymers.[8, 11]	2D maps showing the composition of gel particles and of the continuous phase in phase separated samples

<p>Laser [2-16]</p>	<p>(SERS). In this case, the sample is either deposited on a specifically designed metallic surface, or metallic nanoparticles are incorporated in the hydrogels during sample preparation.[2, 3, 10, 11, 13]</p>	<p>possible heterogeneities, individual particles in phase-separated systems, crosslink nature and location in the hydrogel network, tracking of encapsulated materials even at very low concentrations. Length scale: 10^{-8}-10^{-4} m</p>	<p>depends on the depth in the sample and on the objective used for the experiments (resolution is higher with objectives that minimise the difference in refractive index between the sample and their environment such as oil and water immersion objectives as compared to metallurgic objectives; hydrogel beads below $10\ \mu\text{m}$ can be investigated with immersion objectives) [7, 8] Field of view: between 10s to 100s of μm Magnification: up to 100×</p>	<p>conventional confocal microscopy.[4, 5] Confocal apparatus may be used to obtain 3D images of the samples.[9, 11] Raman signal is proportional to compound concentration which allows for quantification.[2, 7, 8, 14, 16, 17] Multiple components can be imaged simultaneously.[4, 6-8]</p>	<p>Due to the weakness of the signal, data collection may be very long (up to several hours), which limits the use of this technique regarding kinetics studies.[8] Raman signal may be hindered if the sample exhibit fluorescence, which is fairly common for biopolymers. This can usually be avoided by choosing a laser with an excitation wavelength that does not induce fluorescence.[4] Raman spectra of distinct biopolymers often present high levels of similarities and it is sometimes difficult to distinguish them from one another. Advanced data processing and modelling may be required to separate both signals.[4, 7, 8, 14-17] The choice of the objective (metallurgic vs immersion objectives) is important when studying small spherical objects</p>	<p>prepared with 2 biopolymers.[7, 8] In hydrogel single- and multicomponent-beads, biopolymer concentration as a function of the radial position.[5] Spatial distribution of encapsulated compounds in hydrogel beads, [9, 11, 12] with an example involving SERS.[11] <i>Identification of polymer-rich and polymer-depleted regions may be identified since Raman signal is proportional to species concentration leading to the estimation of fluid gel particle size in their native state.</i> <i>Spatial organisation of fluid particles in the samples.</i></p>
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				Raman signal may be significantly enhanced by using SERS, which involves metal nanostructures. [2, 3, 10, 11, 13] SERS-tags are more stable over time than dyes/stains commonly used for confocal microscopy.[11]	as it has a significant influence on the resolution on the z-axis.[7, 8] Sample may be damaged by the laser beam. When using SERS with dispersed metallic nanoparticles, although nanoparticles are usually well dispersed across hydrogel matrices, they may form some clusters which then causes small artefacts with the presence of areas that have an anomalously high intensity on the maps.[2, 11] Metallic nanoparticles may interact with the hydrogel matrix and lead to artefacts.	<i>SERS may be useful to enhance Raman signal. There may be limitations to the use of dispersed metallic nanoparticles therefore, as they have been shown to form small clusters leading to anomalously high signals.</i>
Super-resolution fluorescence microscopy (SRFM) or nanoscopy Laser	If the hydrogel is not self-fluorescent, staining with a fluorescent dye is required. The sample can then	Polymer network homogeneity/heterogeneity at nano scales, cross-linker position and density, local	SFRM can overcome the issues caused by the diffraction limit (200-300 nm in x-y plane and 500-1000 nm in the z-direction) in classical optical microscopy	Once labelling is performed, samples can be observed without any specific preparation. Time-dependent	Fluorescence labelling is required. Care needs to be exerted to avoid disturbing microgels or changing their properties.[23] Non-covalently bound dyes may leach in the microgel environment and increase fluorescence background. When the polymer	Use of a non-covalent fluorescent tag that allows for probing the polarity of the local environment.[24] Characterisation of κ -carrageenan hydrogel network heterogeneous

[18-25]	be observed without any extensive preparation.[18, 25]	differences in environment within microgels, properties of individual microgels (morphology, shape, size, polydispersity, deformation at interfaces), 3D organisation of microgels in the sample (packing, deformation, interpenetration), microgel tracking, study of volume phase transition, location of different components, monitoring of	and allow for optical imaging of nano scales[18, 23] Lateral and z-resolution: depend on the SFRM technique. They may be as low as 1 nm and 30 nm, respectively. See Fig 2 and Tab. 3 of Ref. [18] for details. Field of view: a few μm to 100s of μm	studies can be performed. 3D imaging is possible.[23] Single molecules can be localised.[23] Crosslinking in microgels can be investigated by using fluorescent crosslinkers. Extrapolation of the outcomes obtained with such fluorescently-tagged microgels to untagged microgels need to be exerted with care as tagging is likely	network is too tight, it may not be able to diffuse within the entire volume of a microgel particle (which still gives information about the microgel structure).[23] There is an open question about how representative the collected data are given the heterogeneous nature of microgels and their polydispersity.[23] For some techniques, acquisition time is relatively long and requires more specific preparation of the sample for the particles to be still during the measurements. Fast kinetics or samples where dynamics are too fast cannot be probed in these cases.[19]	nanoscale structure with non-covalently bound fluorescent nanoparticles.[22] Good reviews introducing SFRM techniques and practical aspects such as the choice of appropriate fluorescent tags.[18, 20, 23, 25] Review dedicated to the application of SFRM to probe food structure.[21] <i>SFRM could be a powerful tool to image fluid gel particle properties, especially their shape, size, polydispersity, morphology, polymer and cross-link densities. Their 3D organisation could be probed as well. Individual particles could be tracked</i>
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		gelation over time, study of diffusion/transport phenomena of solutes		to modify some of the microgel properties such as their size.[19, 23]		<i>to better understand ageing phenomena.</i>
		Length scale: 10^{-9} - 10^{-5} μm		Local differences of polymer chain behaviour within the microgels can be probed with fluorophores that fluoresce differently depending on their environment.[20, 23]		
Photon Correlation Imaging (PCI) and Dynamic Light	Transfer in appropriate light scattering cell. Mesogel/microgel/nanogel suspensions as	Probing of spatial heterogeneities in samples, identification of changes in	Field of view and spatial resolution: depend on the set-up. It is limited in all cases by the pixel size of the camera	Sample can be observed without any extensive preparation.	Sample need to be transparent to avoid multiple scattering. In case of significant multiple scattering, space-resolved multispeckle diffusing wave spectroscopy (MSDWS) may be used.[29] For	Heterogeneities and ageing in various hydrogels and colloidal gels.[28, 30, 31]

<p>Scattering (DLS) Lasers [26-35]</p>	<p>well as single mm-size hydrogel beads may be probed (a dedicated set-up has just been developed for this purpose in the latter case).</p>	<p>microscopic dynamics over time (gel network formation during gelation and its evolution afterwards can be probed). When coupled with rheology, the influence of shear and stress on sample microscopic dynamics can be investigated. A recently developed set-up allows for investigating microscopic dynamic changes in singular mm-</p>	<p>used for image acquisition and the magnification. Typically, data are coarse-grained on a spatial scale of <i>ca.</i> 10 μm or more. On the <i>z</i>-axis, they depend on the thickness of the laser beam. Sample of sheets of thickness as low as 60 μm have been explored.[30] In the <i>xy</i>-plane, fields of view as large as the 50-mm diameter disk of rheometer plate geometry can be probed.[32] Smaller fields of view of about 245×1550 μm^2 have been probed.[27] Increasing the size of</p>	<p>A wide range of timescales can be probed from a couple of ms to 10⁻⁴-10⁻⁵ s.</p>	<p>samples exhibiting a small amount of multiple scattering, it may be circumvented by decreasing the thickness of the light scattering cell. In the newly developed PCI set-up to observe hydrogel beads, the size of the hydrogel beads is limited. It can be as small as 1 mm if the refractive index of the hydrogel bead is close to that of the surrounding medium as refraction at the bead-surrounding medium interface is limited. If the difference in refractive index is larger (like for experiments performed in air), hydrogel beads need to be larger, still in the millimetric range.[35]</p>	<p>Changes in sample microscopic dynamic during and after gelation.[33, 34] Effect of shear/stress on sample microscopic dynamics.[26, 32] Drying of hydrogel millimetric beads investigated by coupled PCI and brightfield imaging.[35] <i>Although experimental evidence is still lacking, it is generally agreed that, overall, fluid gels contain polymer-rich and polymer-depleted regions. Since these regions should have a different microstructure, one should be able to visualise them with PCI, provided that they are large enough as</i></p>
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size gel beads
upon various
stimuli. [35]
Length scale:
depends on the
scattering
vector, typically
around a few
100s of nm

the field of view
increases
proportionally the
spatial scale of
coarse-graining.

compared to the coarse-graining length scale. Assuming that the polymer-rich regions correspond to the fluid gel particles or at least their core, an in situ estimate of the fluid gel particle size may be obtained. Comparing the dynamics of both polymer-rich and polymer-depleted regions could also bring some insights about the inner structure of fluid gel particles, and especially help understanding how the particles are packed together and what happens in the interstitial regions.

If the fluid gel particles can be isolated, they may be studied with the set-up

allowing to characterise singular particles, provided that they are large enough.

Dedicated devices coupling both PCI and rheology have been developed. They may be used to image fluid gel particle formation and to link fluid gel rheological properties with their microstructure and microscopic dynamics in an unprecedented way.

Table S2: Review of the characterisation techniques that have been used to characterise fluid gel particles/suspensions so far

Technique	Sample preparation	Information obtained over length scale	Resolution/detection limit, field of view, magnification	Advantages	Disadvantages, damage to sample
Probe [Ref]					
Optical microscopy	Fluid gel suspensions need to be diluted to observe fluid gel particles. Dilution factors are	Fluid gel particle size and shape/morphology,	Lateral resolution: 0.2 μm	Easy sample preparation.	Since sample dilution is necessary to probe something, the structure of

<p>(Direct) Light ($\lambda = 440-700$ nm) [36-46]</p>	<p>usually between 4 and 6. Staining is often required to increase the contrast between the fluid gel particles and their aqueous environment. Most commonly used dyes are methylene blue [42] and toluidine blue.[36, 43]</p>	<p>aggregates of smaller fluid gel particles. Alignment of fluid gel particles under flow was observed with interference contrast illumination.[46]</p>	<p>z-resolution: 2-3 μm Field of view: mm Magnification: up to 100\times</p>	<p>Widely accessible observation technique.</p>	<p>the native fluid gel samples cannot be observed. In quite a few cases, there is not enough contrast between the fluid gel particles and their environment to perform the observations in the brightfield mode. Phase contrast mode [37-39, 41, 44-46] or polarised light illumination [40] have been successfully used instead to image fluid gel particles.</p>
<p>Confocal microscopy (Direct) Laser ($\lambda = 400-700$ nm) [37, 41, 47, 48]</p>	<p>Samples need to be stained if they are not self-fluorescent. Commonly used fluorescent dyes are rhodamine [37, 41, 48] and fluoresceinamine.[47]</p>	<p>Fluid gel particle size and 3D-shape/morphology, spatial arrangement of the fluid gel particles, identification of polymer-rich and polymer-depleted</p>	<p>z-resolution: 0.5 μm z-depth: 200 μm Field of view: mm Magnification: up to 100\times</p>	<p>3D image of non-dilute samples. Artifacts are rare.</p>	<p>Sample can be damaged due to high laser intensity. Samples need to be self-fluorescent [49] or have to be properly dyed or tagged.</p>

		regions, localisation of additives.			
		Length scale: 10^{-6} - 10^{-3} m			
Electron microscopy (SEM, STEM, TEM)	Details about sample preparation is sparse or non-existent for the reference where fluid gel particles are imaged with TEM.[50]	TEM: particle shape, size and internal structure of the particles.	Field of view: TEM: 100 nm SEM: 1 mm	TEM: visualisation of particle shape, size and internal structure.	Image quality depends on sample preparation., working distance, aperture size, acceleration voltage and probe current.
(Direct Accelerated electrons ($\lambda = 10^{-12}$ nm) [43, 50, 51])	STEM: sample diluted by 40 and dried on a sample stage under vacuum.[51] SEM: sample quickly cooled down with liquid nitrogen and freeze-dried overnight.[43]	STEM: differences in polymer concentrations in the fluid gel particles. SEM: observation of the network formed by the fluid gel particles.	Lateral resolution: TEM: 0.2 nm SEM: 2 nm Magnification: up to 5,000,000×	SEM: visualisation of the porous structure.	Sample preparation by drying can damage sample structure and shape. High energy beams can damage sample.
		Length scale: TEM: 10^{-9} - 10^{-6} m SEM: 10^{-9} - 10^{-5} m			

<p>Static Light Scattering (SLS) (Indirect) Laser ($\lambda = 400-700$ nm) [41, 43, 49, 50]</p>	<p>Samples need to be diluted prior to measurements to avoid multiple scattering.</p>	<p>Particle size distribution. Length scale: from a couple of 100s of nm to a couple of mm (the instrument manufacturers advertise that their instrument can probe particles as small as a few 10s of nm, but this is outside the range of the Mie theory which is used to retrieve particle size information from the scattering intensities)</p>	<p>Easy. Quick way to obtain the particle size distribution of a fluid gel sample with appropriate statistics.</p>	<p>Theories used to determine fluid gel particle size distributions assume that the particles have a spherical shape which is rarely the case. The so-obtained size information should therefore be taken with care.</p>
<p>DSC (Indirect) Heat balance [44, 48, 52, 53]</p>	<p>As-prepared samples.</p>	<p>Melting temperature and enthalpy, degree of organisation in the sample.</p>	<p>N.A. Easy and relatively fast. Small sample volume required.</p>	<p>Temperature calibration and standard selection need to be performed rigorously to get accurate results.</p>

		Length scale: 10^{-8} - 10^{-6} m		
Rheology (Indirect) Stress/strain [36-54]	As-prepared samples. Samples may also be prepared <i>in situ</i> , which allows for continuous monitoring of the applied shear.	If the sample is prepared <i>in situ</i> : detection of the point at which fluid gel particles start contributing to the sample flow behaviour. Fluid gel viscoelastic and flow behaviours. Determination of sample apparent yield stress. Properties of fluid gel particles may also be deduced.	N.A.	Geometry needs to be chosen carefully. Water may evaporate during measurements. Sample structure/rheological behaviour may be modified upon loading in the rheometer geometry. Sample may be irreversibly damaged during the measurements due to the application of large strains/stresses.

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